

“Ethnopedagogy and Ethnopedagogical Research (Comprehension of Theoretical and Methodological Approaches)” Book Review

“Ethnopedagogy and Ethnopedagogical Research (Comprehension of Theoretical and Methodological Approaches)” Kitap İncelemesi

Oorzhak, S. Ya. & Oorzhak, Kh. D-N. (2020). *Ethnopedagogy and ethnopedagogical research (Comprehension of theoretical and methodological approaches)*.

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The monograph is devoted to one of the significant and relevant issues of modern pedagogical science — the theoretical and methodological comprehension of ethnopedagogy and ethnopedagogical research. In the context of globalization, the growth of interethnic contacts, and the need to preserve the cultural identity of the people of Russia, the study of ethnopedagogy as a scientific field acquires a particular importance. Modern sociocultural and ethnic trends worldwide actualize the need for deeper consideration and comprehension of the theoretical and methodological foundations of ethnopedagogical research at the present stage.

It is noteworthy that the authors of the reviewed monograph raise one of the key problems of modern pedagogy — the need to integrate ethnopedagogical values into the educational process under conditions of globalization and interethnic dialogue, based on a deeper approach to the theoretical and methodological concepts of modern ethnopedagogy.

At present, pedagogical science contains quite diverse concepts of ethnopedagogical education and upbringing, differing in approaches and content. This problem is considered rather complex, as the educational space of any state intertwines the cultural origins of representatives of different ethnic groups. The educational space of the Republic of Tuva is no exception. In the context of globalization and the preservation of cultural identity of the people of Russia, the study of ethnopedagogy as a field of scientific knowledge becomes particularly significant. The current sociocultural situation, with its features and contradictions in the development of a new civil society, makes the topic and novelty of the approaches presented in the monograph by **S.Ya. Oorzhak and Kh. D-N. Oorzhak “Ethnopedagogy and Ethnopedagogical Research (Comprehension of Theoretical and Methodological Approaches)”** highly relevant and in need of modern scientific comprehension and systematization.

The content of the monograph is presented in two chapters. In the first chapter, the authors thoroughly examine theoretical approaches in the works of leading ethnopedagogies of the country from the standpoint of the scientific basis of the ethnopedagogization of education and indicators of the level of ethnopedagogical culture among the subjects of the educational space. They clarify certain concepts developed and used in ethnopedagogy.

The monograph is distinguished by a logically constructed structure, consisting of interconnected sections, each of which reveals key aspects of the subject:

- the historical and philosophical foundations of ethnopedagogy;
- the analysis of scientific schools and directions of ethnopedagogical research;
- issues of study and assimilation of ethnopedagogical knowledge;
- the expansion of the content of ethnopedagogical knowledge in the light of modern realities.

The authors rely on a wide range of sources: both classical works of Russian and foreign authors, as well as modern research, which gives the work depth and scientific validity.

Considering the problem of forming methodological foundations of ethnopedagogy and ethnopedagogical knowledge in the context of the modern worldview, the authors analyze the richest theoretical and practical experience of past and present ethnopedagogies, as well as the principles of the post-nonclassical scientific paradigm.

By emphasizing the role of the well-known scholar G.N. Volkov in the development of ethnopedagogy and the concept of ethnopedagogical knowledge, the authors underline the importance of the conceptual apparatus in ethnopedagogical research, citing the scholar's view that:

“If folk pedagogy relates to experience and its description, the means and ideas of popular education, then ethnopedagogy is the sphere of theoretical thought, the sphere of science... Ethnic pedagogy studies the features of national character formed in specific historical conditions and preserved thanks to the national system of upbringing, undergoing evolution as living conditions change, along with the pedagogical culture of the people.”

In the opinion of the authors, a major contribution to the systematization of knowledge in ethnopedagogy, as well as the foundation for expanding ethnopedagogical knowledge and research, was made by G.V. Nezdemkovskaya. As confirmation, the authors cite her statements about the interdisciplinary nature of ethnopedagogical research, which is very relevant in modern science. They quote her view:

“In our study, ethnopedagogy is considered as an interdisciplinary branch of the system of humanities, which studies folk culture and pedagogy with the aim of developing their educational potential in modern Russian education, primarily in the conditions of a multiethnic Russian state and the improvement of state educational policy.”

The authors agree with G.V. Nezdemkovskaya's assertion that ethnopedagogy encompasses various fields of human knowledge.

The novelty of the study lies in its comprehensive approach to analyzing the methodology of ethnopedagogy: the authors systematize existing research strategies, develop scientific foundations for further empirical studies in this field, and emphasize the need to design ethnopedagogical models corresponding to the conditions of multinational education in Russia.

The authors conclude that there is a need to specify these models as applied to the educational space of the Republic of Tuva, which, in their opinion, remains an open issue.

In the second chapter, the authors focus on understanding the content of ethnopedagogical knowledge, reflecting on the basic concepts of Tuvan folk pedagogy and many other issues that remain open for beginning researchers in ethnopedagogy (based on the materials of the Republic of Tuva).

Significantly, by emphasizing the need to study ethnopedagogy and master ethnopedagogical knowledge (based on the materials of the Republic of Tuva) as the object and subject of ethnopedagogical research by Tuvan authors, the authors attempt to identify the interdependence of the stages of studying ethnopedagogy and the growth of ethnopedagogical knowledge among students. Ultimately, according to the researchers, this affects the effectiveness of its implementation under conditions of ethnopedagogization of education in the Republic of Tuva.

As an example, they refer to the opinions of G.V. Nezdemkovskaya and other Russian scholars who consider ethnopedagogical knowledge as one of the leading scientific concepts of ethnopedagogy. They cite her definition:

“We understand the following: ethnopedagogical knowledge is knowledge about the culture of a particular ethnic community; about reality and the general ethnic picture of the world; about the essence and content of the complex system of kinship relations, ethno-social roles and their significance in regulating relations between members of an ethnic community; about the goals, content, methods, and means of traditional folk upbringing of ethnic groups...”

According to the authors, researcher A.B. Pankin and many other scholars, whose works are analyzed in the reviewed monograph, draw attention to the need for a modern theoretical understanding of methodological foundations, the development of a holistic approach to them, and the identification of new contradictions in empirical and theoretical research in ethnopedagogy.

Very relevant and timely is the thought expressed by the authors that a systematic and substantive solution to the problems of scientific and methodological support for the comprehension of ethnopedagogical knowledge affects the levels of its assimilation, which are interconnected with ethnopedagogical competencies and ethnopedagogical culture — something very important in the professional structure of every teacher.

The language of presentation is scientifically grounded, the style is consistent, and the structure meets the requirements of a scientific monograph.

The terminological apparatus is clearly defined and used consistently. All chapters are supplemented with conclusions, which facilitate comprehension and make the work structurally complete.

An undeniable contribution of the authors to ethnopedagogical science is the thesis on the necessity of including materials about a specific region in the content of ethnopedagogical education.

Ethnopedagogical research, in particular the comprehension of theoretical and methodological approaches and the use of ethnopedagogical knowledge based on folk culture and folk pedagogy, as noted in the monograph, represents a significant contribution to the development of Russian pedagogical science, especially in the context of actualizing the ethnocultural component of education.

The monograph by S.Ya. Oorzhak and Kh. D-N. Oorzhak “Ethnopedagogy and Ethnopedagogical Research (Comprehension of Theoretical and Methodological Approaches)” is an original scientific study of a high level, possessing both theoretical and practical significance. Alongside a high level of scientific argumentation and reliance on modern research by foreign and Russian scholars, the reviewed monograph is also distinguished by its experience in the practical application of ethnopedagogical models in the educational system of the Republic of Tuva and represents another step in the development of theory and practice in this field.

Overall, the analysis of the content of the reviewed monograph allows us to conclude that, thanks to its solid theoretical and methodological base, as well as its systematic methodological approach, the stated goal has been achieved and the research objectives have been fulfilled. The monograph demonstrates evidence-based argumentation, factual accuracy, specificity, logic, coherence of information, systematicity, and structural integrity. The work displays a high level of scientific reflection, methodological culture, and practical orientation, making it valuable for teachers, methodologists, researchers, and graduate students.

It is recommended for publication and dissemination among the scientific and pedagogical community, and can also be used:

- in scientific research in the field of pedagogy, ethnopedagogy, and ethnocultural education;
- in the training of students and graduate students of pedagogical specialties;
- as a textbook and methodological basis for university and college teachers;
- as a study guide in the fields of “Pedagogy,” “Ethnopedagogy,” “Educational Psychology,” and “Cultural Studies.”

Kaynakça / References

Oorzhak, S. Ya. & Oorzhak, Kh. D-N. (2020). *Ethnopedagogy and ethnopedagogical research (Comprehension of theoretical and methodological approaches)*.

Etik Kurul Kararları / Ethics Committee Decisions

Bu çalışma için etik kurul belgesi gerekmemektedir.

Ethics committee approval is not required for this study.

Yayın Etiği Beyanı / Publication Ethics Statement

Bu makalenin planlanmasından, uygulanmasına, verilerin toplanmasından verilerin analizine kadar olan tüm süreçte “Yükseköğretim Kurumları Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiği Yönergesi” kapsamında uyulması belirtilen tüm kurallara uyulmuştur. Yönergenin ikinci bölümü olan “Bilimsel Araştırma ve Yayın Etiğine Aykırı Eylemler” başlığı altında belirtilen eylemlerden hiçbiri gerçekleştirilmemiştir. Bu araştırmanın yazım sürecinde bilimsel, etik ve alıntı kurallarına uyulmuş; toplanan veriler üzerinde herhangi bir tahrifat yapılmamıştır. Bu çalışma herhangi başka bir akademik yayın ortamına değerlendirme için gönderilmemiştir.

All the rules specified in the “Higher Education Institutions Scientific Research and Publication Ethics Directive” have been complied with in the whole process from the planning of this article to its implementation, from data collection to data analysis. None of the actions specified under the title of “Actions Contrary to Scientific Research and Publication Ethics”, which is the second part of the directive, were not carried out. During the writing process of this research, scientific, ethical and citation rules were followed; No falsification was made on the collected data. This work has not been submitted for evaluation to any other academic publication medium.